

PA-Boot Artifact

The following provides instructions for reproducing the results either in the VM environment (**test.ova**) or by building from the source code (**artifact.gz**). It also explains the directory structure and outlines their link to paper.

Quick test in the VM

Get the artifact

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1nP-HUSvWD10D9Tj54Pjinadg1SCRJRyk/view?usp=drive_link

Above is the link to download the VirtualBox VM image test.ova. (It may take some time)

The VirtualBox VM image contains our formal proofs, the validation framework, the proof-of-concept C-implementation, and the necessary environment for checking them (Isabelle 2024, ARM Foundational Platform, and the libraries installed to build the executable file).

To run it, simply import it into an up-to-date version of VirtualBox (we run on VirtualBox 7.0.8). By default, the VM is configured to use 4GB of RAM and four logical cores; you may need to adjust these settings depending on your system's capabilities.

The VM is preconfigured with Ubuntu 22.04, and both the username and password are set to "test."

Our formalization and the implementation are organized in the following three subdirectories under `/home/test/Desktop/artifact/`:

- **paboot-isabelle**: Contains the formalization of our protocol in Isabelle/HOL
- **paboot-OCaml**: Contains the extracted code in OCaml and associated tests
- **paboot-C**: Contains the C implementations CPA-Boot, along with security and performance evaluations.

Run the code

To run Isabelle

- open a terminal and execute the following command
`/home/test/Desktop/Isabelle2024/Isabelle2024` to open the Isabelle GUI
- open the folder located at `/home/test/Desktop/artifact/paboot-Isabelle`

To run OCaml test

- open the folder located at `/home/test/Desktop/artifact/paboot-OCaml`
- The OCaml code has been pre-compiled, so only execute the command `./proto` to run the code in `/home/test/Desktop/artifact/`

To run C test

- open the folder located at `/home/test/Desktop/artifact/paboot-c`

- run `sudo ./run.sh linux-system.axf` to see the whole boot process running on FVP, with the shell printing counts of CPU cycles in different phrases (i.e., bootwrapper, PA-boot, Gentoo Linux system) as performance evaluation
- run `sudo ./run.sh attack_images/attack*/linux-system.axf ,*` for 1-5 for security evaluation

```
# in folder artifact/paboot-c, run the final executable linux-system.axf on FVP

# implementation: boot the system with normal execution
sudo ./run.sh linux-system.axf
# also for performance evaluation: after the success boot of the system, the
shell prints the number of CPU cycles of CPU0 and CPU1

# security evaluation: boot the system with attacks, * for 1-5
sudo ./run.sh attack_images/attack*/linux-system.axf
```

Build from source

Our source code for formalization and the implementation are organized in the following three subdirectories under the **artifact.gz** file

- **paboot-isabelle**: Contains the formalization of our protocol in Isabelle/HOL
- **paboot-OCaml**: Contains the extracted code in OCaml and associated tests
- **paboot-C**: Contains the C implementations CPA-Boot, along with security and performance evaluations.

Run the code in Ubuntu 22.04 LTS

- for Isabelle proofs, open the Isabelle file **paboot-isabelle** in [Isabelle/HOL 2024](#)
- for OCaml test, follow the instructions below, i.e., **2.1** to install OCaml and related packages and **2.2** and run the test in **paboot-OCaml**
- for C test
 - install the necessary toolchain and build tools as listed below in **3.1**
 - run `./build.sh` in **paboot-C** to build the source file
 - run `sudo ./run.sh linux-system.axf` to see the whole boot process running on FVP, with the shell printing counts of CPU cycles in different phrases (i.e., bootwrapper, PA-boot, Gentoo Linux system) as performance evaluation
 - run `sudo ./run.sh attack_images/attack*/linux-system.axf ,*` for 1-5 for security evaluation

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# in folder artifact/paboot-c, run the final executable linux-system.axf on FVP

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```

1 Isabelle Model

1.1 Link to paper

Paper	Code
high-level specification S_h (Section V.A),	high/hlm.thy
low-level specification S_l (Section V.B, Fig.5, Table II)	low/model_concrete.thy, low/model_basic.thy
high-level property (Section VI.A) --- Property 1 --- Property 2	high/hlm.thy --- AF7-AF11 --- lemma final_hlm_thm
prove of functional correctness (Section VI.B) --- Lemma 1	low/mode_invariant.thy --- lemma inv_invariant2
prove of security properties (Section VI.B) --- Lemma 2.1, 2.2, 2.3	low/normal_execution.thy, low/mim_attack.thy, low/corrupt_flash.thy, low/replace_slave.thy, low/tmp.thy, low/tmp2.thy --- lemma llr1, ll2, llr3 in low/tmp2.thy
refinement proof between S_h and S_l (Section V)	(lemma LF1-LF10) in low/tmp2.thy
executable code extraction (Section VII.B) --- protocol_test	generator.thy ,low/model_concrete.thy --- definition protocol_test in low/model_concrete.thy

1.2 Structure

high/him.thy:

Contains high-level specification of the PA-Boot protocol

low/model_basic.thy:

Contains the basic definitions of state, as well as basic components like messages, keys and agents

low/model_concrete.thy:

Contains the definition of agents/attackers behaviors

low/model_invariant.thy:

Contains the proof of invariants on functional correctness

low/normal_execution.thy:

Contains the protocol's normal execution trace

low/corrupt_flash.thy:

Contains the execution traces with corrupted flash,
i.e., the certificates stored in flash are manipulated

low/mim_attack.thy:

Contains the execution traces with adversarial behaviors of a Dolev-Yao attacker,
e.g., the attacker intercept, modify, or inject a transmitted message in channel

low/replace_slave.thy:

Contains the execution traces with a malicious agent AP,

low/tmp.thy:

Contains auxiliary lemma for tmp2

low/tmp2.thy:

Contains the proof of security properties and model refinement

generator.thy:

Contains code to extract Isabelle model S_l into OCaml code via the Isabelle/HOL extraction mechanism

2 Validation Framework

2.1 Install OCaml and related packages

```
sudo apt install opam # install opam
opam init
opam install ocamlfind # install necessary packages
ocamlfind list | grep unix # make sure the unix package is installed
eval $(opam env)
```

2.2 Run the test

```
# in folder artifact/paboot-OCaml, test the extracted OCaml code
eval $(opam env)
ocamlc -c proto_test.ml
ocamlfind ocamlc -o proto -package unix -linkpkg proto_test.cmo
proto_test_OCaml.ml
./proto
```

2.3 Link to paper

Paper	Code
Validation Framework (Section VII B)	<p>Isabelle/HOL: glue code1 <code>paboot-proof/low/model_concrete.thy#L400</code> + extraction declaration <code>paboot-proof/generator.thy</code></p> <p>OCaml: glue code <code>paboot-OCaml/proto_test_OCaml.ml</code>, <code>protocol_test_paboot-OCaml/proto_test.ml</code>,</p>

3 CPA-Boot Evaluation

3.1 Environment Setup and Toolchain

Toolchain and Libraries

Cross-compile toolchain

- **aarch64-none-elf-gcc**: 11.2.0, can install on [ARM GNU Toolchain](#) or install package with `apt-get`
- **aarch64-linux-gnu-gcc**: 11, can install on [ARM GNU Toolchain](#)

Build Configuration Tools

- **autoconf**: 2.71
- **automake**: 1.15.1

```
wget https://ftp.gnu.org/gnu/autoconf/autoconf-2.71.tar.xz
tar -xf autoconf-2.71.tar.xz
cd autoconf-2.71/
./configure
time make
sudo make install
. ~/.profile
autoconf --version # check version

wget https://ftp.gnu.org/gnu/automake/automake-1.15.1.tar.gz
tar -xf automake-1.15.1.tar.gz
cd automake-1.15.1
./configure
make
sudo make install
automake --version
```

Libraries

- **Newlib (v4.3.0)**: Used as the C library.
- **WolfSSL (v5.3.0)**: Used as the SSL library.
- **PA-Boot**: integrated in bootwrapper's `first_spin` function, when BSP finishes platform initialisation and going to jumps to the kernel, and wakes up AP

- **Linux Kernel (v5.16.0):** Compiled as a kernel image using the default AArch64 configuration, with the AArch64 PMU-related settings disabled in the `.config` file to prevent the kernel from modifying `PMCCNTR_ELO`.
- **DTB:** Device Tree Blob used from TF-A (Trusted Firmware-A).
- **Initrd:** a temporary root filesystem built using Buildroot, with a minimal `/init` script that mount a real filesystem
- **Bootwrapper-AArch64 (v0.2):** initializes the boot process on ARM platforms, integrating the PA-Boot protocol and preparing the system to load the kernel and other components.

Configure bootwrapper use the following command:

```
./configure --host=aarch64-linux-gnu --enable-gicv3 --with-kernel-dir=
<linux/arch/arm64/boot/Image> --with-initrd=<initrd.img> --with-dtb=
<foundation.dtb>" CFLAGS=-mstrict-align -I${NEWLIB_INCLUDE_DIR} -
I${WOLFSSL_INCLUDE_DIR} -O2 -mcpu=cortex-a72"
```

Compile and link the libraries to build `linux-system.axf`

The following are compiled and linked together to build `linux-system.axf`, an executable binary that runs on ARM FVP

```
./build.sh # compile and link the libraries to get the executable file linux-
system.axf
```

Running `linux-system.axf` on ARM Foundation Platform

- `linux-system.axf`: containing the kernel, bootwrapper, and necessary libraries, simulating a complete Linux system on FVP
- `gentoo.img`: a root filesystem based on a Gentoo stage 3 archive, with systemd configured as the init system. Contains the full operating system environment and mounted as the root filesystem after the initrd has initialized the system.

To launch `linux-system.axf` on ARM Foundation Platform, use the following command:

```
--gicv3 --cores 3 --image <path-to-linux-system.axf> --block-device <path-to-
gentoo.img>
```

3.2 Implementation and evaluation

```
# in folder artifact/paboot-c, run the final executable linux-system.axf on FVP

# implementation: boot the system with normal execution
sudo ./run.sh linux-system.axf
# also for performance evaluation: after the success boot of the system, the
shell prints the number of CPU cycles of CPU0 and CPU1

# security evaluation: boot the system with attacks, * for 1-5
sudo ./run.sh attack_images/attack*/linux-system.axf
```

3.3 Link to paper

Security Evaluation (Section VII C)

Paper	Executable
AP replacement	paboot-c/attack_images/attack1/
CA certificate compromise	paboot-c/attack_images/attack2/
slave certificate compromise	paboot-c/attack_images/attack3/
man-in-the-middle attack for resp-chall packet	paboot-c/attack_images/attack4/
man-in-the-middle attack for resp packet	paboot-c/attack_images/attack5/